

**Dendrochronological dating of the World Trade Center ship, Lower
Manhattan, New York City.**

Dario Martin-Benito¹, Neil Pederson¹, Molly McDonald², Brendan Buckley¹, Paul Krusic³,
Kevin Anchukaitis¹, Rosanne D'Arrigo¹, Laia Andreu-Hayles¹, and Edward Cook¹.

Affiliations:

1, Tree-ring laboratory, Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory of Columbia University. 61
Route 9W, Palisades, NY 10964. USA

2, AKRF, Inc. 440 Park Avenue South, New York, NY 10016. USA

3, Bert Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Department of Physical Geography and
Quaternary Geology, Stockholm University, SE-106 91 Stockholm. Sweden

Abstract

On July 2010, archaeologists monitoring excavation at the World Trade Center Site (WTC) in Lower Manhattan encountered the remains of a portion of a ship's hull. Because the date of construction and origin of the timbers were unknown, samples from different parts of the ship were taken for dendrochronological dating and provenancing. After building a floating 280-year long chronology from the extracted white oak samples, we used 21 oak site chronologies to evaluate absolute dating and provenance. Our results showed the higher agreement between the WTC chronology and two chronologies from Philadelphia ($r=0.36$; $t=6.3$; $p<0.001$; $n= 280$) and eastern Pennsylvania. The year 1773 showed the strongest evidence for the tree felling date prior to construction. Our analysis suggested that the oak timbers used to build the ship likely originated from the same specific location, lending credence to the independent hypothesis from idiosyncratic aspects of the vessel's construction that the ship was the product of a small shipyard. Few 18th century ships have been found and there is little historical documentation of how vessels of this period were constructed. Therefore, ship's construction dating to 1773 is important in confirming that the hull encountered at the World Trade Center represents a rare and valuable piece of American shipbuilding history.

Introduction

Since the time of early Dutch settlement, shipping was one of the most important economic activities of New York City. In 1647 the Dutch West India Company built the first docks and wharfs in New York (Buttenwieser, 1987). In 1664, the English occupied and took possession of New Amsterdam, renaming it New York. In 1686 lands and water bodies within the island were transferred from the British Crown to the City of New York. Soon after, waterfront property was sold to private owners who in most cases extended their property with landfill. Since that time the coast line around the island of Manhattan has undergone extensive physical alterations (Squires, 1992). Cheap and abundant fill materials, such as rocks, earth, and waste, were retained within wood structures to create new land. Earlier wharfs and abandoned merchant ships were often subsumed within newly constructed land.

On July 13, 2010, archaeologists monitoring excavation for a Vehicular Security Center at the World Trade Center Site encountered the intact remains of a portion of a ship's hull (Figure 1). The vessel remnant was recovered from landfill deposits approximately one city block west of Manhattan's original shoreline at Greenwich Street; approximately 300 meters east of the present coastline (AKRF September 2012). The World Trade Center was built between 1966 and 1971 by the Port Authority of New York and New Jersey on land that had been filled between roughly 1760 and 1818; the location where the ship was found had been filled by the 1790s (AKRF, 2012). Our hypothesis is thus that the ship was built in the mid to late 18th century before sinking either deliberately or accidentally.

The important of dendroprovenancing for mobile wooden artifacts

Determining the dates of construction of wooden structures was one of the first applications of dendrochronological techniques (Douglass, 1921; Douglass, 1929). One of the major limitations of dendroarcheology of shipwreck material is establishing the origin of the timbers used for construction and the shipyard where it was built (Farrell and Baillie, 1976). A similar limitation is encountered when dating other mobile wooden artifacts such as furniture or artwork (Haneca et al., 2005; Bridge, 2012). Thus, simultaneously with the process of correctly dating these timbers, it is of paramount importance to identify their origin or provenance. This process, called dendroprovenancing (i.e. the use of tree rings to identify the region of origin for wooden material), has been most commonly and successfully used in western Europe where the lack of abundant local timber sources forced the use of imported timber from the Baltic sea area already in the 14th century (Bridge, 2012). Success in dendroprovenancing requires a dense network of site regional chronologies for different species from potential areas of origin. Such a network exists for the eastern US where tree-ring width chronologies have been developed for many sites using drought sensitive tree species (e.g. Stahle and Hehr, 1984; Stahle et al., 1985; Stahle and Cleaveland, 1988; Stahle et al., 1998; Cook et al., 1999; Pederson et al., 2012a; Pederson et al., 2012b). In addition, previous dendrochronological work to date historical buildings in the eastern US (Grissino-Mayer et al., 2012; Therrell and Stahle, 2012), including the Independence Hall in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania (Cook and Callahan, 1992), allowed for the extension of tree-ring records both in space and back in time. This kind of network expansion facilitates further dendroarcheological work (Stahle and Wolfman, 1985).

According to the number of publications on this matter, dendroarcheology has been a less common practice in the eastern US than in southwestern US (Robinson,

1976; Stahle and Wolfman, 1985; Grissino-Mayer, 2009). Although numerous structures have been dated in the eastern US (e.g. Cook and Callahan, 2004; Krusic et al., 2004; Cook and Callahan, 2005; Grissino-Mayer et al., 2012; Therrell and Stahle, 2012), a minority of these investigations have been published in academic journals or their reports and data made publicly available (but see e.g. Huber (2006), McDonald (2006), and the Boston Dendrochronology Project http://www.dendrochronology.net/boston_project.asp#). Similarly to what has happened in the southeastern US (Grissino-Mayer, 2009), the northeastern US has been traditionally considered too mesic to develop reliable tree-ring width chronologies that show good agreement with other chronologies at the regional level and thus for correctly dating wood artifacts. However, because common responses to wide climatic patterns create similar tree-ring patterns across wide geographical regions (Fritts, 1976), there has been a long history demonstrating the pervasiveness of drought sensitivity across ecosystems in the eastern US (Cook and Jacoby, 1977, 1983; e.g. Stahle and Hehr, 1984; Stahle et al., 1985; Cook et al., 1999; Pederson et al., 2012a; Pederson et al., 2012b) and new research indicates drought sensitivity across forest strata and land-use histories (Pederson et al., 2012b), it is clear that these networks can also be convincingly used to date historic timbers and to identify the region of origin of these dated timbers.

Dendrochronological dating and provenancing of recovered shipwreck remains have been more commonly used in Europe mainly for vessels from northern countries (e.g. Bonde and Christensen, 1993; Daly, 2007; Daly and Nymoer, 2008). These techniques have been much less often applied in North America (Pickard et al., 2011) although dendroprovenancing of timbers has been used when the date of construction was not in question (Carrell, 2003). Here we report on what might be the first application of dendrochronology to date the remains of a ship in the northeastern coast of the US.

Dating and determining the origin of timbers from a wreck buried in New York City, one of the world's busiest ports since the 1600s could have been quite challenging. Fortunately, all but one of the timbers sampled were identified as white oak (*Quercus alba* L). Having multiple samples of the same species for comparison improves the likelihood of dating archaeological timber samples of unknown site origin. Perhaps just as important for provenance work, the other sample belonging to the keel of the vessel was identified as hickory (*Carya*), a sample we think is likely to be shagbark hickory (*Carya ovata* (Mill) K. Koch). The presence of timbers from this hickory species hickory reduces the possibilities of the place of construction to East US or East Asia (Manos and Stone, 2001). Thus, our primary hypothesis is that these timbers originated in the eastern US.

Material and Methods

The WTC Ship was found approximately 22 feet below ground surface, oriented east-west. The stern section of the hull, which pointed west, was the most intact section, measuring 32.5 feet long and 14.5 feet wide (Figure 2). The ship had been bisected by a slurry wall built as part of the ongoing construction along the former line of Washington Street. A small section of the bow was later found on the east side of the slurry wall. The ship remnant consisted of the lower hull of a vessel. With the exception of a small orlop deck at the stern end, none of the decks or upper portions of the ship survived. The archaeologists carefully recorded the vessel remnant *in situ* (Figure 3). Each piece of timber that comprised the structure was labeled with unique identification number. The hundreds of individual timber elements were then carefully disassembled, packed into a storage container, and transported to a conservation laboratory for stabilization. The physical characteristics of the ship remnant, including the broad beam, shallow draft, and

forward-stepped mast, appeared consistent with a class of ship known as the Hudson River Sloop, designed to transport goods and passengers along the Hudson River (Norman Brouwer, personal communication).

The remains of Teredo worms (“shipworms”) infested many of the ship’s timbers, particularly the sternpost, outer planks, and frames. After examination of a sample of the infested wood it was determined that a single species was represented, *Lyrodus pedicellatus* (Kevin J. Eckelberger, personal communication). This species is typically found in warm waters with high salinity. This, combined with the absence of any shipworm species local to the northeastern United States led to hypothesize that the larvae may have infested the sternpost in the Caribbean (Kevin J. Eckelberger, personal communication).

Species wood analysis showed that a variety of wood types had been used to serve particular functions in the ship’s construction (Robert A. Blanchette, personal communication). The keel (the spine of the ship) was of hickory (*Carya*, sp., Figure 4) and the keelson (the member that runs directly above the keel) of white oak (*Quercus* sp.). The sternpost and stern knee, large timbers comprising the stern end, were also white oak (Figure 4). The frames of the ship (the essential structure of the hull, including floor timbers, futtocks, and cant frames) were also white oak. The vessel remnant had two layers of planking: outer planking, which formed the exterior of the hull, and ceiling planking, which formed the interior of the hull. In several locations, sections of the vessel’s plank floor appeared to be patched with replacement planks. Sample planks taken for species identification showed that several woods were used, including spruce (*Picea* sp.), pine (*Pinus*, sp.), and white oak (*Quercus*, sp.). The orlop deck was also floored in spruce (*Picea* sp.) planks. All of the major timbers of the vessel remnant were hewn and were principally fastened using iron spikes.

Sample preparation

Complete wood pieces were carefully removed from the construction pit (Figure 2) and transported under high humidity conditions to the Maryland Archaeological Conservation Laboratory in Saint Leonard, Maryland where they were submerged in water until sampled. Pieces that were considered to contain a reasonable number of growth rings were selected for sampling. A chain saw was used to cut radial sections from 23 of the logs (see C-SPAN Video Library: World Trade Center Ship. URL: <http://www.c-spanvideo.org/program/CenterSh>). Sampling location in the mid-sections of each piece was wrapped with duct tape to ensure the stability of the wet wood pieces. Because of the location where the samples were found all of them were water logged. Thus previous to further preparation the samples were slowly air dried under cool temperature to avoid cracking associated with rapid shrinking. Further splitting and cracking could impair sample analysis. Another potential issue with dating submerged, historical samples is that the wood could have decomposed to such a degree that the structure of the wood would be too compromised for processing. Therefore, some of the more decayed pieces were glued onto wood boards in order to facilitate processing. None of the samples presented any evidence of bark. However, nine samples had sapwood rings (Figure 4), which would suggest that the last dated ring is near the felling date of the tree. Seven samples showed evidences of being squared prior to construction of the vessel, which reduces the amount of rings present and thus the probability of finding the last ring formed before felling (Miles, 1997).

Measuring and crossdating

After drying, the samples were sanded with progressively finer sandpaper until tree rings were clearly visible. Two radii per section were marked along the radial

transects containing the maximum number of growth rings and visually crossdated to assure within tree relative dating for all the rings (Stokes and Smiley, 1968). Tree-ring widths on all samples were later measured to the nearest 0.001mm using a Velmex measuring stage. Internal crossdating of the two radii within each sample was then checked using COFECHA (Holmes, 1983). Radii from different samples were also relatively dated among themselves. We created a vessel chronology from the relatively-dated series using ARSTAN (Cook and Holmes, 1984) by detrending each series using flexible cubic smoothing spline 50% wavelength cutoff of 32 year to remove age-related trends and the possible effect of stand dynamics from where the trees were growing to leave most of the high frequency variability in the time series. These detrended series were averaged using a robust estimation of the mean to create a standard chronology.

This residual chronology containing all successfully crossdated samples was used for absolute dating by comparing it with master tree-ring width chronologies for white oak from 21 different sites across Northeast United States (Figure 4) using COFECHA. We limited this analysis to master chronologies dating back at least to the year 1650. Chronologies from several sites were used in an attempt to identify the geographical origin of the wood sample and probably the site of construction of the vessel (Bridge, 2012). In all cases we tested 50 years successively lagged 25 years against the reference master chronologies using the nonparametric Spearman rank correlation coefficient with significance level of $p=0.01$.

Results

There were several limitations to the dating of the WTC vessel timbers. First, the keel, keelson, and seven other timbers were squared off prior to construction. Because of this, there was only a small chance that the last ring formed before felling is present

on these timbers. Second, although nine samples show signs of curvature and sapwood rings, which is indicative of the outer surface of a tree stem, no samples were found to have intact bark. Bark is commonly lost after long periods of submersion under water. Third, the sapwood rings (the growth rings located just inside the bark on a stem of a tree) in some samples were either expanded or contracted by the long time the timbers had been waterlogged and were either extremely narrow or wide with little intra-annual growth variability (Figure 4). These ring patterns reduced our ability to date the outermost available rings to the level of statistical significance specified. In addition, the rotted conditions of sample CN-5-1 did not allow for sanding and ring measuring and was thus removed from further analysis.

A little more than 50% of the samples (12 of 23) had less than 100 rings (Table 1), which is considered the minimum desirable number of rings for cross-dating historical or archeological timbers in the eastern United States. However, tree-ring patterns in the timbers sampled displayed statistically significant internal crossdating with series correlations with the WTC chronology from the 19 dated series ranging from 0.24 to 0.62 (all significant at $p=0.05$; Table 1). Therefore we used the biweight robust estimation of the mean to produce a WTC chronology to date it against different site chronologies in the eastern US. Despite the keel being a different species than the rest of the samples, we attempted crossdating it against the WTC chronology. While there is some confidence of its date of 1724, its related statistics are weak ($r = 0.25$); the date should be considered provisional until more hickory chronologies covering the mid 17th century become available for the eastern US. Finally, there were two oak samples (OUT? and FN-11-1/1) that did not yield any conclusive dating against this local chronology despite having 83 and 99 rings respectively.

Because of the unknown provenance of the timbers, we first had to identify the area from where they originated. In order to do this, we correlated the WTC chronology, restricted to the period with 5 or more series (i.e. 170 years from 1599 to 1769), against 14 chronologies from the eastern US to test our second hypothesis. The highest correlation coefficient is with a chronology developed with historical timbers from the Philadelphia area ($r=0.36$, $t=6.40$; $p<0.001$; $n=280$) followed by a chronology from eastern Pennsylvania ($r=0.35$; $t=6.30$; $p<0.001$; $n=280$). (Table 2; Figure 2). In general, correlation was high with all but one of the chronologies used from the Pennsylvania, New Jersey-Southern New York (PANJNY) area (Table 2; Figure 6 and 7). In contrast, correlations with chronologies from the northern Hudson valley yielded non-significant coefficients, as was also the case for other sites to the south and west of the PANJNY area.

The strongest evidence for the tree felling date prior to construction was found for sample FN-16-1 whose last ring was dated to 1773 (Table 1 and 2). In addition there were three other samples with last present rings dating to 1770 and one dating to 1769. The presence of sapwood in these four samples suggested a close proximity to missing bark and thus to the cutting year. In contrast, the earliest outer ring was found to be 1650 in sample CN-1/1. This sample did not present sap wood rings and could thus be missing an unknown number of rings. In general, samples from timbers had had been squared for construction and had no sapwood rings yielded earlier dates than those with sapwood rings.

Discussion.

Dendroprovenance

A ship mainly built with timbers from the white oak group (*Quercus* section *Leucobalanus* or section *Quercus*) found in New York City, could have very diverse origins. Oak species of the section *Leucobalanus* thrive in different parts of the world, including some of the most widely used timber oak species such as *Quercus alba* L. (East North America), *Q. petraea* (Matt.) Liebl and *Q. robur* L. (Europe and West Asia) or *Q. aliena* Blume (East Asia) (Nixon, 2006). From the 17th century onwards there was a constant traffic across both sides of the Atlantic Ocean, so the WTC ship could have been built most likely on a shipyard in either Europe or North America. At least one study has documented a 17th century shipwreck off the North American coast of a ship built with oaks in Western France (Carrell, 2003). But, the presence of an essential piece of the ship like the keel made of hickory, indicates that the place of construction for this ship is likely to be the eastern US. Although, the possibility remains that the original keel had been replaced with American timbers, it is estimated that by 1770's at least 40% of all British ships were built with American timbers (Williams, 1992; p. 93). Therefore, we focused dating the WTC timbers against site master chronologies from the eastern US dating back at least to 1650.

Our results showed that the higher agreement was between the WTC chronology and two master chronologies from Philadelphia and eastern Pennsylvania (Table 2; Figure 7). Lower but significant correlations were found with other master chronologies in New Jersey and Southern New York. The lack of dating from the northern portion of the Hudson Valley in eastern New York State is intriguing in that it is only 315-400 km from Philadelphia. The lack of correlation here compared to stronger correlations in central Pennsylvania and central Virginia indicates a fairly sharp climatological boundary in the

northern Hudson Valley. This finding is similar to evidence of a changing climatic response in *Quercus alba* moving up the Hudson valley (Pederson et al., 2004) and difficulty in dating a historical piece of *Quercus alba* from the Mohawk Valley (N. Pederson, unpublished data), which is just adjacent and to the west of the northern end of the Hudson Valley. The individual series correlations of the WTC samples with the WTC chronology suggests that most if not all of the timbers used to build the ship came from the same tree population or, perhaps, the same forest around the Philadelphia area.

The very narrow width of tree rings found in the samples analyzed (1.05 ± 0.06 mm year⁻¹; Figure 4) suggested that these trees most likely originated from old growth forests. These primeval forests were greatly impacted by human activities following the earliest European settlers in the northeastern US as soon as the early as the 17th century (Williams, 1992). Logging was first carried out along the major waterways and the coast and then continued further inland. Reduced competition in the forest stands created conditions for faster growth and wider tree rings not observed in the samples analyzed.

Dating

According to the outer rings dated for all the WTC samples, the construction of the ship was not likely to be prior to 1773. There were four samples with felling dates at 1770 or later and three more with dates after 1762 (Table 1). Although we did not observe bark in any of the samples, all samples dating to 1762 or later presented many sapwood rings suggesting that not many rings, if any, formed after the identified last ring were missing (Hughes et al., 1981). These results would support the hypothesis of an early 1770's construction date for the ship. Dates of 1732 and 1743 for the last tree rings

of two samples with sapwood rings would be inconsistent with this construction date. Assuming that not many rings if any are missing from the edges of these two samples, it would suggest that the timbers might have been obtained from an already dead tree or reuse of older timbers which might have been a common practice (Farrell and Baillie, 1976). Further, sample OUT-8 (dated to 1732) was dislocated from the ship remnant when it was found and although it appeared to represent a displaced ship frame, there is a possibility that the sample was not part of the ship. The rest of the timbers dating back as early as 1650 had clear signs of having been squared prior to construction; no waney edge or sapwood rings were present in these samples. Therefore, the last tree rings dated for these samples can only be interpreted in support of a *terminus post quem* (earliest possible) date of 1773. Since landfilling of the site where the ship was uncovered was finished by the 1790s (AKRF, 2012) that would be the latest possible period of construction. Assuming the older date of 1773 as the date for the felling of the trees, we can conclude a construction date of mid to late 1770s allowing a few years for the seasoning of the wood at most (Farrell and Baillie, 1976). These results would imply that the vessel was in operation for at most 20 years before being abandoned or sinking in what was then a harbor on the west side of Lower Manhattan.

A close examination of the WTC and the Philadelphia master chronologies shows two simultaneous reductions of growth in the late 1660's and 1690's supporting the hypothesis that the trees used to develop both chronologies originated from the same locality. Most likely the shipyard where the ship was constructed was close to where the trees were felled. This evidence appears to support a hypothesis put forth by Norman Brouwer (personal communication), who stated that based on certain idiosyncratic aspects of the vessel's construction, it may have been built at a small rural shipyard rather than a large, established and well-financed shipyard (AKRF, 2012). A small

shipyard may have been more likely to take limited timber stock from a single geographic location for the construction of a vessel. According to Scharf and Westcott (1884), shipbuilding was an important industry in eastern Pennsylvania and Philadelphia from as early as 1693 through the 1770's. In 1698, the shipyards in the city were observed to "have very stately oaks to built ships with" (p. 2336) and "logs of pine, hemlock, and oak are cut for ship frames, wharf timbers" (p. 2244), suggesting that at the time adequate timber for ship-building was almost certainly available in the Philadelphia area.

The dendrochronological analysis provided a number of crucial insights into the history and origin of the World Trade Center ship. First, it provided an approximate construction date for the ship. Few 18th century ships have been found archaeologically and little historical documentation of how vessels of this period were constructed survives. Therefore, confirmation of the ship's date was important in confirming that the hull encountered at the World Trade Center represented a rare and valuable piece of shipbuilding history. The identification of a construction date also pointed to the mysterious fact that ship had a short life span before being subsumed within landfill. Hard use, repairs, and shipworm infestation may have contributed to the ship's demise. Evidence that the vessel may have made at least one trip to the Caribbean suggests that although the ship was constructed for use in a river environment, it may have actually been used to transport cargo much further afield, possibly undermining the condition of the vessel. The dendrochronological analysis also confirmed the ship's American origin, and yielded surprising evidence that the ship was likely constructed in the Philadelphia area, causing archaeologists and maritime historians to reevaluate the initial theory that the ship was a sloop type associated with the Hudson River. Lastly, the analysis suggests that the oak timbers used to build the vessel frame likely originated in the same

specific location, lending credence to the notion that the ship was the product of a small shipyard.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank the Lower Manhattan Development Corporation, the Port Authority of New York and New Jersey, and the project team, including the archaeologists and historians of AKRF, including A. Michael Pappalardo, Elizabeth Meade, and Diane Dallal, consulting maritime historians including Carrie Atkins Fulton, Warren Riess, and Norman Brouwer, and the Maryland Archaeological Conservation Laboratory. We thank Kevin J. Eckelberger (Professor of Marine Biology and Director of the Darling Marine Center at the University of Maine) and Robert A. Blanchette, (Department of Plant Pathology at the University of Minnesota). Thank you also to Javier Martín Fernández for assistance during sample preparation and processing. Two anonymous reviewers provided suggestions that helped improve an earlier version of this manuscript. Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory Contribution No. XXX. D. M-B was supported by a Fulbright-MICIIN postdoctoral fellowship.

References

1. AKRF Inc., 2012. Data Recovery and Analysis of the 18th Century WTC Ship, World Trade Center Memorial and Development Plan. Draft Report prepared by AKRF Inc, submitted to the Lower Manhattan Development Corporation
2. Bonde, N., Christensen, A.E., 1993. Dendrochronological dating of the Viking Age ship burials at Oseberg, Gokstad and Tune, Norway. *Antiquity* 67, 575-583.
3. Bridge, M., 2012. Locating the origins of wood resources: a review of dendroprovenancing. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 39, 2828-2834.
4. Buttenwieser, A., 1987. *Manhattan Waterbound: Planning and Developing Manhattan's Waterfront From the Seventeenth Century to the Present*. New York University Press, New York.
5. Carrell, T.L., 2003. From forest to fairway : hull analysis of 'La Belle', a late seventeenth-century French ship. In, *Maritime Studies*. University of St Andrews.
6. Tree-Ring Laboratory, Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory, Columbia University, New York., 1992. The Development of a Standard Tree-Ring Chronology for Dating Historical Structures in the Greater Philadelphia Region.
7. Tree-Ring Laboratory, Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory, Columbia University, New York, 2004. Tree-Ring Dating of the Dismantled Timbers of the Daniel Pieter Winne House, Bethlehem, New York.
8. Tree-Ring Laboratory, Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory, Columbia University, New York, 2005. A Dendrochronological Analysis of the West Camp House.
9. Laboratory of Tree-Ring Research, 1984. User's manual for program ARSTAN. Tucson
10. Cook, E.R., Jacoby, G.C., 1977. Tree-ring-drought relationships in the Hudson Valley, New York. *Science* 198, 399-401.
11. Cook, E.R., Jacoby, G.C., 1983. Potomac River Streamflow Since 1730 as Reconstructed by Tree Rings. *Journal of Climate and Applied Meteorology* 22, 1659-1672.
12. Cook, E.R., Meko, D.M., Stahle, D.W., Cleaveland, M.K., 1999. Drought reconstructions for the continental United States. *J. Clim.* 12, 1145-1162.
13. Daly, A., 2007. The Karschau Ship, Schleswig-Holstein: Dendrochronological Results and Timber Provenance. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 36, 155-166.
14. Daly, A., Nymoer, P., 2008. The Bøle Ship, Skien, Norway—Research History, Dendrochronology and Provenance. *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 37, 153-170.
15. Douglass, A., 1921. Dating our prehistoric ruins: how growth rings in trees aid in the establishing the relative ages of the ruined pueblos of the southwest. *Nat. Hist.* 21, 27-30.

16. Douglass, A.E., 1929. The secret of the Southwest solved by talkative tree rings. *Natl. Geogr. Mag.* 56, 736–770.
17. Farrell, A.W., Baillie, M.G.L., 1976. The Use of Dendrochronology in Nautical Archaeology. *Irish Archaeological Research Forum* 3, 45-55.
18. Fritts, H.C., 1976. *Tree Rings and Climate*. Blackburn Press, Caldwell, New Jersey.
19. Grissino-Mayer, H.D., 2009. Preface An Introduction To Dendroarchaeology In the Southeastern United States. *Tree-ring Res.* 65, 5-10.
20. Grissino-Mayer, H.D., Maxwell, J.T., Harley, G.L., Garland, N.A., Holt, D.H., Absher, C., Beale, B.J., Boehm, M.S., de Graauw, K.A., Rautio, A.-M., Dye, A.W., 2012. Dendrochronology reveals the construction history of an early 19th century farm settlement, southwestern Virginia, USA. *J. Archaeol. Sci.*
21. Haneca, K., Wazny, T., Van Acker, J., Beeckman, H., 2005. Provenancing Baltic timber from art historical objects: success and limitations. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 32, 261-271.
22. Holmes, R.L., 1983. Computer-assisted quality control in tree-ring dating and measurement. *Tree-Ring Bull.* 43, 69-78.
23. Huber, G.D., 2006. Abbott Lowell Cummings' Prescience and Dates for First Period Houses of Massachusetts Bay Colony Using Dendrochronology. *Material Culture* 38, 39-52.
24. Hughes, M.K., Milsom, S.J., Leggett, P.A., 1981. Sapwood estimates in the interpretation of tree-ring dates. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 8, 381-390.
25. Tree-Ring Laboratory, Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory, Columbia University, New York, 2004. *Tree-Ring Dating of the Cahn House New Paltz, New York*.
26. Manos, P.S., Stone, D.E., 2001. Evolution, Phylogeny, and Systematics of the Juglandaceae. *Ann. Mo. Bot. Gard.* 88, 231-269.
27. McDonald, T.C., 2006. The Fundamental Practice of Fieldwork at Colonial Williamsburg. *Perspectives in Vernacular Architecture* 13, 36-53.
28. Miles, D., 1997. The Interpretation, Presentation and Use of Tree-Ring Dates. *Vernacular Architecture* 28, 40-56.
29. Nixon, K.C., 2006. Global and Neotropical Distribution and Diversity of Oak (genus *Quercus*) and Oak Forests. In: Kappelle, M. (Ed.), *Ecology and conservation of neotropical montane oak forests*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany, p. 483.
30. Pederson, N., Bell, A.R., Cook, E.R., Lall, U., Devineni, N., Seager, R., Eggelston, K., Vranes, K.J., 2012a. Is an Epic Pluvial Masking the Water Insecurity of the Greater New York City Region? *J. Clim.*
31. Pederson, N., Cook, E.R., Jacoby, G.C., Peteet, D.M., Griffin, K.L., 2004. The influence of winter temperatures on the annual radial growth of six northern-range-margin tree species. *Dendrochronologia* 22, 7–29.
32. Pederson, N., Tackett, K., McEwan, R.W., Clark, S., Cooper, A., Brosi, G., Eaton, R., Stockwell, R.D., 2012b. Long-term drought sensitivity of trees in second-growth forests in a humid region. *Can. J. For. Res.* 42, 1837–1850.

33. Pickard, F., Robichaud, A., Laroque, C.P., 2011. Using dendrochronology to date the Val Comeau canoe, New Brunswick and developing an eastern white pine chronology in the Canadian Maritimes. *Dendrochronologia* 29, 3-8.
34. Robinson, W.J., 1976. Tree-ring dating and archaeology in the American southwest. *Tree-Ring Bull.* 36, 9–20.
35. Scharf, J.T., Westcott, T., 1884. *History of Philadelphia, 1609-1884, Volume 3.* Everts & Co, Philadelphia.
36. Squires, D.F., 1992. Quantifying anthropogenic shoreline modification of the Hudson River and Estuary from European contact to modern time. *Coastal Management* 20, 343-354.
37. Stahle, D.W., Cleavelan, M.K., Hehr, J.G., 1985. A 450–year drought reconstruction for Arkansas, United States. *Nature* 316, 530–532.
38. Stahle, D.W., Cleaveland, M.K., 1988. Texas Drought History Reconstructed and Analyzed from 1698 to 1980. *J. Clim.* 1, 59-74.
39. Stahle, D.W., Cleaveland, M.K., Blanton, D.B., Therrell, M.D., Gay, D.A., 1998. The Lost Colony and Jamestown Droughts. *Science* 280, 564-567.
40. Stahle, D.W., Hehr, J.G., 1984. Dendroclimatic Relationships of Post Oak across a Precipitation Gradient in the Southcentral United States. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers* 74, 561-573.
41. Stahle, D.W., Wolfman, D., 1985. The Potential for Archaeological Tree-Ring Dating in Eastern North America. *Advances in Archaeological Method and Theory* 8, 279-302.
42. Stokes, M.A., Smiley, T.L., 1968. *An introduction to tree-ring dating.* University of Chicago Press, Chicago, Illinois, USA.
43. Therrell, M.D., Stahle, D.W., 2012. Tree-Ring Dating of An Arkansas Antebellum Plantation House. *Tree-ring Res.* 68, 59-67.
44. Williams, M., 1992. *Americans and their Forests: A Historical Geography.* Cambridge University Press.

Table 1. Internal dendrochronological dating results for samples taken from the excavated WTC ship. All correlations (R) are Spearman rank correlations of each individual series against the WTC chronology (built with all other series). The keel was dated against the chronology developed from the WTC oak samples. See Figure 1 for a summary plot of the dating results for all dated samples. Bark edge was not recovered or was completely missing on all the timbers.

Sample	Species	Obs.	Series			Years compared					
			FY	LY	N	FY	LY	N	R	T	P value
FN16-1	Oak	SWR	1663	1773	111	1663	1770	108	0.44	5.02	<0.001
FS13-2	Oak	SWR	1688	1770	200	1688	1770	83	0.49	5.09	<0.001
FS11-2	Oak	SWR	1571	1770	83	1571	1770	200	0.45	7.08	<0.001
FS15-2	Oak	SWR	1682	1770	89	1682	1770	89	0.36	3.55	<0.001
FN15-1	Oak	SWR	1627	1769	143	1627	1769	143	0.46	6.22	<0.001
FN15-1/1	Oak	SWR	1662	1764	103	1662	1764	103	0.32	3.37	<0.001
FS10-2	Oak	SWR	1689	1762	74	1689	1762	74	0.55	5.54	<0.001
FS9-2	Oak	SWR	1680	1743	64	1680	1743	64	0.46	4.11	<0.001
Keelson	Oak	SQ	1639	1740	102	1639	1740	102	0.43	4.78	<0.001
OUT-8	Oak	SWR	1641	1732	92	1641	1732	92	0.58	6.78	<0.001
CN3-1	Oak		1662	1732	71	1662	1732	71	0.43	4.01	<0.001
FS12-2	Oak	SQ	1600	1723	124	1600	1723	124	0.54	7.10	<0.001
OUT-W	Oak		1660	1721	62	1660	1721	62	0.39	3.27	<0.001
PS1-1	Oak	SQ	1665	1716	52	1665	1716	52	0.46	3.71	<0.001
CN6-1	Oak	SQ	1644	1705	62	1644	1705	62	0.38	3.22	0.001
PS2-1	Oak	SQ	1602	1687	86	1602	1687	86	0.64	7.63	<0.001
PN2-1	Oak	SQ	1559	1685	127	1559	1685	127	0.61	8.71	<0.001
CN3-10A	Oak	SQ	1542	1681	140	1542	1681	140	0.59	8.69	<0.001
CN-1/1	Oak		1494	1650	157	1542	1650	109	0.20	2.12	0.018
CN-5-1	Oak		n.d.	n.d.	NA	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
OUT?	Oak		n.d.	n.d.	83	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
FN-11-1/1	Oak	SQ	n.d.	n.d.	99	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
Keel	Hickory	SQ	1581	1724	144	1581	1724	144	0.25	3.06	0.001

FY, first year; LY, last year, N, number of years compared; R, Spearman rank correlation coefficient; T, student's t-test; SWR, sapwood rings present; SQ, squared timber. n.d., no date; NA, not applicable because the conditions of sample CN-5-1 did not allow for sanding and ring counting

Table 2. Correlation matrix of the WTC ship oak chronology versus long oak chronologies from the eastern US. See Figure 7 for a map of correlations. Correlation values are Spearman rank correlation coefficients. Chronology sites are in decreasing order of latitude from north to south.

Master chronology	Years compared					P value	Lat	Lon	Source ¹
	FY	LY	N	R	T				
Prospect Mountain	1659	1773	115	0.04	0.67	0.250	43.50	73.62	1
Albany	1710	1773	64	0.13	2.24	0.013	42.40	74.00	2
Albany historic	1507	1773	267	0.11	1.77	0.039	42.40	74.00	1
Eastern Massachusetts	1494	1773	280	0.24	4.10	<0.001	42.30	71.30	2
Mohonk Preserve	1494	1773	280	0.27	4.70	<0.001	41.74	74.19	1
Hudson Valley	1563	1773	211	0.29	5.00	<0.001	41.46	74.08	2
Schunemunk Mountain	1648	1773	126	0.21	3.58	<0.001	41.39	74.11	1
Uttertown	1494	1773	280	0.29	5.10	<0.001	41.19	74.42	1
PA006	1662	1773	112	0.06	0.97	0.166	41.19	79.13	ITRDB
Alan Seegar Nat. Area	1516	1773	258	0.19	3.20	<0.001	40.72	77.75	
OH001	1629	1773	145	0.06	0.98	0.164	40.53	81.45	ITRDB
Huchenson Forest Historic	1494	1773	280	0.32	5.60	<0.001	40.30	74.34	1
Eastern New Jersey	1620	1773	154	0.33	4.20	<0.001	40.30	74.34	2
Philadelphia	1494	1773	280	0.36	6.40	<0.001	40.04	75.16	3
Eastern Pennsylvania	1494	1773	280	0.35	6.30	<0.001	40.00	75.30	2
OH006	1628	1773	146	0.08	1.26	0.104	39.59	81.00	ITRDB
OH003	1666	1773	108	-0.09	1.57	0.941	39.54	84.24	ITRDB
VA014	1615	1773	159	0.11	1.89	0.030	38.30	78.21	ITRDB
VA017	1572	1773	202	0.20	2.90	<0.001	37.55	79.48	ITRDB
VA011	1554	1773	220	0.18	3.07	0.001	37.23	80.30	ITRDB
NC007	1620	1773	154	0.05	0.76	0.225	35.53	81.56	ITRDB

FY, first year; LY, last year; N, number of years compared; R, Spearman rank correlation coefficient; T, student's t-test; Lat, latitude (°N); Lon, longitude (°W); ITRDB, International Tree-Ring Data Bank. ¹, sources: 1) Pederson et al. (2012a), 2) E. Cook, 3) Cook and Callahan (1992).

Figure captions.

Figure 1. The ship as it was encountered during excavation for a Vehicular Security Center at the World Trade Center Site in Lower Manhattan. The ship was 22 feet below current ground surface. Courtesy of the Lower Manhattan Development Corporation.

Figure 2. Vertical 3D laser scanning image of the ship *in situ* World Trade Center Site in Lower Manhattan. The hull of the ship was 32.5 feet long and 14.5 feet wide. Courtesy of the Lower Manhattan Development Corporation and Corinthian Data Capture

Figure 3. Archeologists carefully labeled and disassembled all individual timbers of the ship. They were packed into storage containers, and transported to the Maryland Archaeological Conservation Laboratory in Saint Leonard, Maryland. Courtesy of the Lower Manhattan Development Corporation.

Figure 4. White oak, *Quercus alba*, sample (A) and hickory, *Carya* sp, keel sample (B). Box in image (A) shows the general slow growth of these trees which suggests they most likely originated from old growth forests.

Figure 5. Top, horizontal histogram of time spans for all WTC ship timbers dated. Bottom, plot of the 19 ring-width indices from the WTC ship oak samples (black) and their mean (red; 280 years; time span: 1494-1773). The strong mean interseries Spearman rank correlation (0.458; $p < 0.001$) suggests a common geographical origin for all the timbers. In both graphs, results for the keel (hickory) are shown in green.

Figure 6. Comparison of the ring-width index of the WTC ship oak chronology (19 samples cross-dated) against the Philadelphia area oak master chronology based on living trees and independent archaeological samples. The Spearman rank correlation between the series ($r=0.36$) is highly significant ($t=6.3$; $p<0.001$) with an overlap of 280 years. This strong match suggests that the origin of the oak logs used in the WTC ship was from the Philadelphia area.

Figure 7. Map of the Northeast US showing the strength of the WTC ship chronology (green triangle) against site white oak master chronologies. Dot size is proportional to the strength of the t-test value for significant correlations ($p<0.01$). Chronology sites with non-significant correlations (n.s; $p>0.01$) are marked by black squares. Higher correlations with master chronologies in eastern Pennsylvania suggest the trees used for building the WTC ship were growing in that area.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4 (A)

Figure 4 (B)

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

